

LINGUODIDACTIC DESCRIPTION OF DISCURSIVE COMPETENCE AND ISSUES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a linguodidactic analysis of discursive competence as a component of the communicative competence of future primary school teachers, revealing its essence and developmental factors. In the process of professional education, future teachers are required to demonstrate flexibility, dynamism, a creative approach, the ability to quickly adapt to new conditions, and to conduct innovative professional activities, along with the development of skills in thinking, programming, and planning. The elimination of shortcomings encountered in oral and written speech is envisaged, as well as the development of speech in monologic and dialogic forms.

At the global level, in educational processes of global significance, the issue of developing the professional training of future specialists is becoming particularly relevant. In advanced educational centers in developed countries (such as the Center for Creative Leadership Courses, IEDP, MOOC, CPC), creative and communicative abilities are recognized as key qualities. In particular, the necessity of possessing a high level of discursive and communicative competence is emphasized, as well as readiness for various forms of interaction (verbal, written, nonverbal) with individuals of different ages, statuses, and social positions, serving as an example for others. This, in turn, is of significant importance for ensuring that during professional education, the future teacher is flexible, dynamic, possesses inherent creative potential, can quickly adapt to new conditions, and conduct innovative professional activities.

In the course of our research, we considered it appropriate to study issues related to the development of students' discursive competence.

In the process of developing discursive competence, researchers distinguish the following stages:

- 1.informational-analytical;
- 2.practical-developmental;
- 3.generalizing-developmental [1].

There are significant differences in teaching dialogue and monologue; however, it is also important that "the teaching of dialogic and monologic speech should occur simultaneously from the very beginning of the language course" [2].

In our research, we studied the following linguodidactic principles aimed at developing discursive competence (Figure 1).

Regarding the principle of awareness of the purpose of one's own speech acts – the preliminary characteristics of the form of speech are preparedness, awareness, motivation, and initiative. Primarily, as the most crucial stage of speech, it is necessary to consider the following, which are distinguished as separate stages:

- Cognitive activity;
- Planning;
- Programming.

In oral speech, a communicative intention of a strategic nature, which implies the possibility of posing a question, often cannot be fully realized by the speaker. The specific nature of the motivational sphere of speech requires considering the state of communicative interaction between the speaker and the listener at the moment of speech production. If a communicative motive is present in oral speech, a state of dialogue often arises, and the speech proceeds in a less cohesive form compared to written strategic speech.

The principle of communicative situation analysis, aimed at forming discursive competence, involves achieving goals through the parameters of a secondary communicative situation, taking into account the communicative action of the subject aimed at achieving a communicative goal. The characteristics of the activity are explained in oral and written speech and differ depending on the form of speech and the state of the communicative act.

In oral speech, all characteristics inherent in coherence and integrity are determined in its initial version through processing and clarification of information. In this process, the necessity of considering the features of each speech form is key to the formation of discursive competence.

Many researchers interpret the term "discourse" as "a holistic speech act that embodies various cognitive and communicative functions" [3].

However, current approaches to forming discursive competence are insufficient because in communication, the main focus is not the meaning of the text or its linguistic form, but how it is expressed and serves as a tool for achieving the communicative goals of the partners. Unlike a text, in speech, a coherent text – considered from the perspective of a speech event together with modeled extralinguistic factors (pragmatic, social, mental, and others) – governs the communicative situation. This means that speech, as a component of purposeful

social action, is viewed from the perspective of cognitive processes and the formal construction of speech, as well as thinking processes of various types, actualized and linked to extralinguistic factors, as the interaction of people.

Some researchers note that "teaching aimed at developing critical thinking skills involves not only students actively seeking information to assimilate, but also something more: linking what they learn to their own experience, as well as comparing what has been learned with other research in that field of knowledge" [4].

Based on these requirements, a competency-based approach is also incorporated into the methodology of teaching the native language, founded on the requirements for creating a new generation of textbooks. It is assumed that the development of linguistic competence during the lesson will contribute to the improvement of speech competence. Based on the clear qualification requirements for teaching the native language, the further development of methodological capabilities for listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills is relevant today. These issues enhance the significance of the research topic.

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